

This study indicates that derivatives of the cross Vijaya/W12787 are highly susceptible to false smut, while those from W1263/W12787 exhibit a degree of resistance. The other two crosses, Jaya/W1263 and Sona/W1263, have intermediate resistance to false smut.

Yield losses due to sheath blight of rice

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We studied yield losses due to sheath blight on the moderately resistant variety IR26 and the highly susceptible line IR1487-372-1-1 at three levels of disease intensity (10, 20, and 50% hills inoculated) at 0 and 100 kg N/ha during the 1975 dry and wet planting seasons at IRRI.

In IR26, the percent yield reduction per unit of disease rating was 2.7 in the plots with 0 N and 2.3 in the plots with 100 kg N/ha. But yield reductions were significant only at the highest level of disease incidence in the plots with higher nitrogen during the dry-season trial. Reductions were insignificant at both N-levels in the wet season. In IR1487 the percent yield reduction per unit of disease rating was 4.4 in the 0 N plots and 4.3 in the 100 kg N/ha

Sheath blight reduced yields significantly on the susceptible line IR1487-372-1-1 at all levels of disease intensity and nitrogen fertilizer; yields were significantly reduced on the moderately resistant variety IR26 only at the highest levels of disease intensity and nitrogen. IRRI, 1975.

Hills inoculated (%)	Yield losses (%) at		Yield ^a (t/ha) at	
	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha
<i>IR1487-372-1 (susceptible)</i>				
0	—	—	5.7 a	5.8 a
10	7.5	8.6	5.2 b	5.3 b
20	12.2	13.8	5.0 b	5.0 c
50	22.7	23.7	4.4 c	4.4 d
<i>IR26 (moderately resistant)</i>				
0	—	—	6.1 a	7.8 a
10	0.4	2.5	6.2 a	7.6 a
20	6.5	5.1	5.7 a	7.4 a
50	8.8	13.2	5.6 a	6.8 b

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not statistically different at the 5% level.

plots. The levels of disease incidence at both nitrogen levels were statistically significant. The highest percentage of yield loss was about 13 percent for IR26 and 23 percent for IR1487 (see table).

Correlations between disease rating

and yield losses showed that the susceptible variety was very sensitive to the disease—yields decreased rapidly as disease incidence increased in both the 0 and 100 kg N/ha plots. The moderately resistant variety was less affected by the disease (see figure).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistances

Resistance in some rice strains to first-instar larvae of *Tryporyza incertulas* (Walker) in relation to plant nutrients and anatomical structure of the plants

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The degree of resistance to first-instar larvae of the rice stem borer and the interaction of resistance with certain important plant cell ingredients were studied during 1972–73 in seven rice strains that differ in resistance. To study the possible effects of silica application in inducing stem borer resistance in the rice plant, potassium silicate at 5 g/pot was applied 1) at the time of sowing; 2) during transplanting; and 3) at 7 days after transplanting. The possible effects

on ease of penetration for the larvae and on their survival were also studied. The studies were confined to the first-instar larvae of the rice stem borer on seedlings of Eshwarakora, TN1, W1263, TKM-6, IR20, HR59, and B5580.

There was no uniformity in site of penetration into the plant, larval survival after penetration, or larval ability to cause dead hearts. The uptake of added silica varied among different rices; the variation affected larval survival and growth. The higher silica uptake in IR20 and HR59 led to the wearing and defacing of the insects' mandibles and interfered with the boring and feeding capacity of the larvae. Higher silica content was related to higher insect mortality in IR20, Eshwarakora, and TKM-6; silica content was negatively

IR1487-372-1-1 shows rapidly decreasing yield with increasing intensity of sheath blight disease. Yields of IR26 demonstrate less sensitivity to the disease.